

ASSESSMENT OF VISCO ELASTIC WAVE PROPAGATION IN FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES CAUSING DELAMINATIONS

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Abstract: Impact induced elastic wave propagation in continuous fiber reinforced composite material is investigated with a special emphasis on the thickness direction. Due to wave reflection at the boundary delamination failure may occur. This phenomenon is assessed using analytical, experimental and numerical approaches and the results are compared. Especially the experimental procedure for wave propagation measurement and the determination of failure strengths at elevated strain rates is discussed.

1. Introduction

Most impact scenarios involving structural components made of laminated composite materials cause significant loading proportions in the materials thickness direction. The subsequently induced elastic wave propagation through the composite material can be described and the resulting strain information may be used for failure analysis. Such layered structures typically exhibit a significantly lower tensile strength in thickness direction in comparison to the respective compression strength. The initially compressive wave components introduced at the impact location return as tensile waves due to wave reflection at a free boundary and may subsequently initiate delamination failure.

2. Analytical Approach and Experiments

Wave propagation characteristics can be described applying the 1D wave equation in laminate thickness direction. The MAXWELL model is used represent the material response in terms of the resulting strains:

$$\varepsilon_3'' - \frac{1}{c^2}(\ddot{\varepsilon}_3 + \frac{1}{\eta}E_3\dot{\varepsilon}_3) = 0 \quad .$$

The solution is based on the LEE/KANTER [1].

Besides the characterisation of the delamination initiation strengths and failure strains at elevated loading rates [2,3], the elastic wave propagation is experimentally investigated. For that, a novel impact testing rig is presented (Fig. 1b). The impactor acceleration is based on electromagnetic induction induced by eddy currents. A coaxial impact of the cylindrical impact partners (impactor: Aluminium, target: composite (Fig. 1a), is achieved by guiding the impactor in the barrel. A nearly coplanar impact contact results in an idealised 1D-wave propagation of the induced impulse in the specimen.

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Figure 1. (a) Multi-stage manufacturing method for cylindrical specimens (thickness 200 mm);
(b) Impact test setup based on electromagnetic induction

3. Results

Two types of experiments are conducted: sub-critical ones to investigate the wave propagation characteristics and critical ones in which the specimen fails and the delamination initiation can be investigated. The measured strain wave propagation results (using strain gauges, SG) in specimen thickness direction are assessed with regard to the varying impulse shape, amplitude and duration. Exemplarily, in Fig. 2 results of a critical test are shown. They indicate highly non-linear propagation behaviour and a wave shape transformations during travelling towards the reflective boundary.

Figure 2. (a) Comparison of experimental, analytical and numerical wave propagation results;
(b) Delamination initiation due to wave reflection

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